

Research programme of the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) 2014 – 2016

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I. Remit and structure of the BfR

The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) is the scientific body of the Federal Republic of Germany that prepares expert reports and opinions on questions of consumer health protection on the basis of internationally recognised scientific assessment criteria and then formulates courses of action for risk minimisation based on the analysis of risks. The BfR is independent in its assessments, and the findings of these assessments are made available to the public at large, the world of science and other involved or interested parties.

The BfR cooperates in the scientific field with other national and international institutions and organisations active in the areas of consumer health protection and food and feed safety. One of the focal points of its operations in this respect is cooperation with the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and, with regard to the assessment of the health hazard of chemicals, with the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA). Through its involvement in bodies on national (e.g. Ministry of Education and Research (BMBWF), German Agricultural Research Alliance (DAFA)) and international level (such as the EU, WHO, OECD), the BfR also plays a role in the definition of research strategies and funding priorities, underpinning the worldwide connections of the institute. All in all, BfR scientists sit on more than 350 bodies. Through its involvement in these bodies (BVL, Section 64 of the German Food and Feed Code (LFGB), DIN, CEN) and the network of national reference laboratories (NRLs), the BfR plays a key role in the ongoing development, harmonisation and standardisation of methods and procedures.

The BfR performs tasks in line with, among other laws and regulations, the following:

- The "Act Concerning the Reorganisation of Consumer Health Protection and Food Safety" of 6 August 2002 (the "BfR Act")
- laws on food and feed
- laws on zoonoses
- laws on plant protection
- laws on biocides
- laws on chemicals incl. the REACH Regulation
- laws on genetic engineering
- laws on protection against infection
- laws on dangerous goods
- laws on detergents and cleaning agents
- German Animal Welfare Act

The aforementioned legal framework has assigned the specific following tasks to the BfR:

- Preparation of scientific reports, opinions and statements on issues directly or indirectly connected to food safety, biological safety, product safety, chemical safety and consumer protection with regard to human health. This includes nutrition, nutritional prevention and animal health - to the extent that it concerns feed, feed additives, the trade in and use of medicinal products intended for use in animals and pharmacologically active substances used in animals, with the exception of animal vaccines
- Provision of scientific advice to federal ministries (Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL), Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (BMUB) and Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure (BMVDI)) and other higher federal authorities, to the extent that the BfR performs activities within the remit of these ministries and authorities, as well as to the Federal Office of Consumer Protection and Food Safety (BVL) on all issues related to the activities of the BfR
- Cooperation with the services of the European Union, in particular the European Food Safety Authority as well as with other scientific institutions on national and international levels, and coordination of the exchange of scientific information in the fields of food safety and consumer protection
- Scientific research where this is closely linked to the activities of the BfR
- Assessment of the threat to health from chemicals, including implementation of the REACH REG, documentation and information on poisoning incidents
- Documentation of notifications of formulations for chemical products that contain hazardous mixtures as well as for biocides, detergents and cleaning agents
- Consultation of Länder Authorities and of committees for the protection of animals with regard to acquisition, breeding, housing, maintenance and usage of vertebrates and cephalopods
- Consultation of Länder Authorities regarding matters related with alternatives to animal experiments
- Consultation regarding the regulatory relevance and suitability of alternative approaches to animal experiments envisaged for validation on EU level
- Publication of non-technical project summaries of approved projects with animal experiments
- Recording and assessment of methods to replace and supplement animal experiments
- Risk assessment in the case of genetically modified animals, plants and microorganisms where these are used to produce food or where they impact food, as well as genetically modified feed and feed additives

- Health issues related to the transport of dangerous goods as well as the approval of plants and processes for ballast water treatment
- Involvement in monitoring of zoonoses and food monitoring
- Assumption of role as national reference laboratories (NRLs) in line with Regulation (EC) 882/2004
- Provision of information to the public at large in its fields of activity on health risks and on other experience gained and work results obtained
- Information and advice for the German government regarding the effects of plant protection products on the health of humans and animals

In its capacity of national EFSA Focal Point, the BfR coordinates the exchange of scientific information between the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the authorities responsible for food and feed safety in Germany and stakeholders from the business community, political circles, the sciences and consumer associations.

Eight departments are responsible for performing these specialised tasks:

Risk Communication Department

Consumer health protection involves research into risks as well as the assessment and communication of these risks. Risk communication and therefore the tasks of the department are based on international standards and extend far beyond the forwarding of information of the usual kind. In this context, it is not just the risks themselves that are important but also their communication in the media and how they are perceived. Scientific findings must be transparent and put across in a comprehensible manner in order to promote a rational response to risks. BfR has the statutory remit for risk communication and informs the public at large about possible health risks and the research findings on which they are based in the fields of food, chemical and product safety. To this end, BfR enters into an active dialogue with various stakeholders from science, industry, political circles, the media, associations, non-governmental organisations and consumers. Besides target-group orientated press and public relations, this communication process entails the active involvement of various interest groups in expert meetings, status seminars, consumer protection forums, stakeholder conferences and public symposiums staged by the "BfR Academy". The department is also responsible for coordinating communication in the event of crises and for deriving strategies to prevent crises.

The interdisciplinary Risk Communication Department conducts research projects on risk perception, early risk detection and risk impact assessment in fields such as new technologies like nanotechnology, changes in nutritional behaviour of consumers following risk communication or the ranking of risks by various social interest groups. The tools used here are representative surveys, consumer conferences, Delphi surveys and focus groups. In order to

carry out these special measures, the department also has funds at its disposal to take advantage of external expertise.

Exposure Department

In this department methods for the exposure assessment are developed further and are standardized within an international collaboration as well as data for the exposure assessment are collected. The department is lead in the conduct of the first German Total Diet Study (TDS) and in the feeding survey for children (KiESEL) and functions as reference for exposure assessment at the BfR. It is also responsible for the cross-departmental functions of information technology and quality management. The department also acts as the GLP federal office.

Its tasks include the assessment of health risks during transport, in particular the marine transport of dangerous goods and the assessment of health risks in the context of ballast water management. In addition, the department is responsible for the documentation of poisoning incidents and product formulations for in-house assessments and as a source of information for the poison information centres in Germany. Other core tasks include the application and when indicated enhancement of biostatistical and mathematical methods and respective advice to the units in the BfR, support in the area of quantitative risk assessment, the development of risk assessment methods and the preparation of opinions on epidemiological statistical studies. The joint appointment of quantitative risk assessment and exposure modelling created together with the University of Veterinary Medicine Hannover (TiHo) expands the scope of these activities.

Biological Safety Department

The central activities of this department comprise the identification of health risks to humans due to microorganisms and the toxins formed by these microorganisms in and on food and feed, cosmetics and consumer items. The focus is on microbiological risk assessment of the pathogens that are mainly responsible for food infections and intoxications as well as those present in feed. In addition, the department is responsible for analysing the spread of pathogens along the food chain as well as for preparing quantitative risk assessments and developing safety concepts in the area of food and product hygiene, developing and the improvement of modern methods for pathogen diagnosis including genome analysis, recording and assessing antimicrobial resistance, and assessing the emergence of or detecting new pathogens or pathogen variants in food and feed due to horizontal gene transfer or the effects of climate change. In addition, the department investigates the safety of product supply chains, also with regard to risk assessments and safety concepts for the recording and prevention of the intentional release of pathogens and toxins into the food and feed chain.

The National Reference Laboratories (NRLs) for *Campylobacter*, *Escherichia coli* including Verotoxigenic *E. coli*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, Coagulase-positive Staphylococci including *Staphylococcus aureus*, Trichinellas, Monitoring the Viral and Bacteriological Contamination of Bivalve Molluscs, Antimicrobial Resistance and the NRL for the Analysis and Testing of Zoonoses (*Salmonella*) work within the department. The consiliary laboratories for *Yersinia* and *Leptospira* are also part of the Biological Safety Department.

Food Safety Department

Ingredients in food are always a potential source of health risks. The Food Safety Department therefore conducts toxicological assessments of food ingredients in non-processed and processed foods, assesses the health risks of novel and genetically modified foods, and carries out assessments of food products taking into account aspects from nutritional sciences and nutritional medicine including allergies. This is an area in which health risks to especially vulnerable sections of the population also play a role.

In order to integrate its assessment activities with research approaches, the department develops and uses modern molecular and cell-biological methods. For this purpose, new biological end points for the risk assessment of potentially risky substances ("nutrigenomics, proteomics") are identified. The development and application of effect-based analytical methods paves the way for the detection of contaminants and residues and/or the identification of their biological effects *in vitro*. One central aim is to provide modern, rapid and low-cost monitoring methods for food control purposes. When investigating the relevant issues, human studies are conducted to determine oral bioavailability and to identify and quantify biomarkers of exposure, effect and individual sensitivity. Within the context of work on molecular traceability and authenticity, the NRL for Animal Protein in Feed and the Reference Laboratory in the Network of Genetically Modified Organisms (GMOs) are assigned to the department.

Safety of Pesticides Department

According to the legal remit of the BfR regulatory issues have priority especially in this department. The central tasks of the department therefore comprise the health assessment of pesticide preparations (plant protection products and biocides) as well as their active substances and metabolites. This assessment involves - as elements of risk assessment - the determination of inherent toxic properties and dose-effect relationships for the purposes of classification and labelling, the derivation of limit values and calculation of risk to consumers, users and non-involved third parties due to exposure. In addition, the department reviews analytical monitoring methods and develops new or optimises existing regulatory testing methods and strategies.

The assessments prepared in the department are used in national, European and worldwide processes. They form the basis for national and European approval and licensing procedures as well as risk management measures.

Research of the department shall have close references with the regulatory work, therefore the research activities of the department support this work by ensuring the cross-departmental further development of methodological and conceptual principles of risk assessment in the fields of toxicology and exposure assessment. Applying innovative research approaches and modern molecular and cell biology methods together with other departments of BfR the current focus is above all on questions relating to the cumulative assessment of mixtures like in multiple residues and preparations, the improved and harmonised assessment of skin absorption of pesticides, the calculation of processing factors for residue assessment and the further development of harmonised principles for assessment in Euro-

pean admission procedures particularly for degradation products and metabolites in soil and ground water.

Chemicals and Product Safety Department

The department is responsible for the health assessment of chemicals and consumer products. The emphasis is on the assessment of chemical substances based on European chemical law (REACH Regulation (EC) 1907/2006) and CLP Regulation (EC 1272/2008) as well as the health assessment of consumer products. The key factors here are whether and to what extent consumers come into contact with the substances contained in products and the potential health risks posed by these substances. This calls for knowledge of the numerous substances and materials and the way they are processed to make the various products. In this connection, the department investigates potential health risks in particular due to:

- cosmetic products like make-up, skin cream, toothpaste, soap or shampoo
- commodities like packaging and containers for food, hygiene products, toys, clothing, detergents and cleaning agents
- body jewellery and tattoos
- tobacco products
- other consumer items like furniture, mattresses, carpets, hobby articles etc.

Using the insights of the overall assessment as a starting point, the department conducts research in the field of chemicals and product safety. These activities profit to a major degree from the high level of interdisciplinarity between toxicology and analytics as well as from the department's excellent connections on both national and international level. The current focal points of experimental work are the investigation of migration, absorption (skin/lung) and local and systemic toxicity. This also encompasses questions relating to toxicologically relevant mechanisms, biochemistry and molecular biology, toxicokinetics, the identification and effect of potential endocrine disruptors, and the eukaryotic and commensal metabolism of relevant chemicals, also taking into account novel compounds like nanoparticles. In addition, the department investigates the influence of material properties and production methods on consumer exposure, with particular emphasis on the carcinogenic, mutagenic, reprotoxic and sensitising properties of substances (allergenicity). Modern techniques (e.g. "omics", complex cell cultures and stem cells) are used for this purpose. Moreover, the development of analytical methods for the detection of elements used in consumer products, including nanoparticles, also plays a particular role. The department houses the NRL for Materials Envisaged for Contact with Food.

Safety in the Food Chain Department

The occurrence of contaminants, residues and other undesired substances in food and feed necessitates the assessment of risks to humans resulting from the intake of these substances from food. Analysis of the entry pathway and the quantity of these substances as well as changes in food and feed is necessary in order to assess the hazardous potential. The focus is therefore on the development of innovative detection methods and on collecting data as a basis for exposure assessment. Reference laboratory activities are also part of the department's remit. The NRLs for Dioxins and PCBs, Mycotoxins in Food and Feed, Monitoring of Marine Biotoxins and Additives for Use in Animal Nutrition, and the Senior Expert Office for

the Import Control of Wine in line with the Wine Monitoring Ordinance are assigned to the department.

As part of the core theme of product identity and traceability, the department develops strategies and methods for the authenticity testing of food and the safety of product supply chains, as adulteration in the form of additives or other illegal practices can pose a threat to consumer health. Within the framework of animal experiments on agricultural livestock, investigations are conducted into the carry-over of undesired substances from feed into foods of animal origin. This allows monitoring of the entire supply chain from farm to fork.

Experimental Toxicology and ZEBET Department

The activities of the Experimental Toxicology and ZEBET Department (ZEBET is the Centre for the Documentation and Evaluation of Alternatives to Animal Experiments) comprise the (further) development of alternatives to animal experiments based on the 3R principle and of modern molecular-toxicological methods and assessment strategies as well as investigation of toxicodynamic and mechanistic and toxicokinetic aspects for the purpose of risk assessment. Within the context of a joint appointment created together with the Charité Medical School in Berlin, the department cooperates closely with universities and other research institutions.

ZEBET develops and validates alternative non-animal experimental methods based on the 3R principle with the aim of replacing or at least minimising the number of animal experiments not only during approval procedures but also in the field of fundamental research. One of the main aims during implementation of the 3R concept is to promote the "refinement" principle; animal welfare and laboratory animal science are therefore two priorities of the department and are being addressed within the framework of a university chair created jointly with the Freie Universität in Berlin.

The department is also responsible for covering the special information needs of the BfR in the field of toxicological alternative methods and assessment strategies in the context of consumer health protection in general and for the production of animal reference material for the NRLs as well as for the rearing and keeping of animals used in experiments (laboratory animals, production animals, aquacultures) for research projects.

With the amendment of the Animal Welfare Act and of the provision for laboratory animals in 2013 the department Experimental Toxicology and ZEBET has new statutory remits. It is responsible for e.g. consulting Länder Authorities and committees for the protection of animals with regard to acquisition, breeding, housing, maintenance and usage of vertebrates and cephalopods. It advises on issues related with alternatives to animal experiments and publishes non-technical project summaries of approved projects in the internet.

Reference laboratories

Reference laboratories are laboratories with special expertise in specific areas that are appointed on the basis of Community or national regulations. In addition to possessing specialist expertise as reflected by, among other things, their involvement in internationally networked research projects and published articles in reputed special-interest journals, they are

also characterised by a high level of independence and are active in EU-wide networks. Alongside routine investigations, the primary job of reference laboratories is to develop and validate methods and to conduct comparative laboratory tests and round robin trials for the purpose of quality assurance. By virtue of the type of work they are involved in, these laboratories perform a "watchdog" role for the early detection of emerging risks and they are of increasing importance for exposure assessments on national - and increasingly also on international - level.

The following reference laboratories (NRLs) are attached to the BfR:

- NRL for the Analysis and Testing of Zoonoses (Salmonella)
- NRL for *Escherichia coli* including Verotoxigenic *E. coli*
- NRL for Parasites (particularly Trichinina, Echinococcus and Anisakis), Subject Group *Trichinella*
- NRL for *Campylobacter*
- NRL for Coagulase-positive Staphylococci including *Staphylococcus aureus*
- NRL for Monitoring the Viral and Bacteriological Contamination of Bivalve Molluscs
- NRL for Antimicrobial Resistance
- NRL for Animal Proteins in Feed
- NRL for Additives for Use in Animal Nutrition
- NRL for Mycotoxins
- NRL for Dioxins and PCBs in Feed and Food
- NRL for the Monitoring of Marine Biotoxins
- NRL for Materials Envisaged for Contact with Food
- NRL for *Listeria monocytogenes*.

In addition, the Senior Expert Office for the Import Control of Wine in line with the Wine Monitoring Ordinance and the Reference Laboratory in the Network of Genetically Modified Organisms (GMOs) perform tasks that are equivalent to those performed by the reference laboratories.

The BfR is a consiliary laboratory for

- Yersinia and
- Leptospira.

II. Research at the BfR

The BfR conducts its own research based on its core fields of expertise and cooperates with other institutions, particularly those in the portfolio of the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture, as well as with universities, the member states of the European Union and international partner countries. The research activities of the BfR are designed to promote the institute's national and international connections. In the development of methods and procedures, the focus is on standardisation on a high scientific level, particularly in an international context.

The BfR has a modern experimental infrastructure for chemical analysis, microbial diagnostics, toxicology and food technology. The institute also comprises an agricultural enterprise with livestock, aquaculture and facilities for experimental animal testings. Moreover, the BfR houses state-of-the-art molecular / cell biology and protein chemistry laboratories to develop alternatives for animal experiments. The large and small-animal laboratory can perform tasks up to security level S2/L2, while microbiological work is possible up to level L3. This means the BfR is in a position to conduct cross-departmental and interdisciplinary investigations and assessments along the entire supply and product chain. The activities of the BfR are based on the relevant ISO standards and recognised standards for quality management, and the institute's laboratory units for analysis, microbiology and toxicology are accredited in line with the standard DIN EN ISO/IEC 17025. In addition, the BfR has been certified according to DIN EN ISO 9001 since 9 August 2010. The institute therefore employs a quality management system in line with international standards both in the area of practical laboratory work, in its scientific assessment processes and in the field of administration. The research work of the BfR is geared towards the recommendations of the German Research Foundation (DFG) based on the principles of good scientific practice

(<http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/349/principles-of-good-scientific-practice-in-the-bfr.pdf>).

II.1 Research goals of the BfR

The BfR views assessment, the preparation of expert reports and research as a single entity. The overarching research goals of the BfR are:

- To offer competent advice to political decision-makers of a high scientific standard based on internationally recognised expertise
- To guarantee the quality of assessments for authorisation/approval tasks
- To strengthen competence within the network of European scientific authorities in the field of consumer health protection
- To safeguard high-quality scientific expertise for the exchange of ideas, concepts and when conducting joint research projects on national and international level
- To create an atmosphere of scientific excellence to increase the attractiveness of workplaces at the institute
- To analyse risk perception of various stakeholders in the fields of science, industry and politics as well as in the media, associations, non-governmental organisations and among consumers as the basis for the development and application of suitable participatory tools for risk communication

II.2 Main areas of BfR research

The BfR primarily conducts research in fields in which risk assessments are necessary. The generated data, methods and techniques form the basis for assessments and policy advice in line with the latest knowledge and insights. The institute's research activities also include work of a non-experimental nature. The main areas of research are based on the BfR's statutory remit and are defined every two years in a research programme.

In order to implement this programme, the BfR not only funds its own research but also acquires public third-party funding. In addition, the BfR also has funds at its disposal that it can award to third parties so that it can draw on external expertise to meet research requirements.

The research activities of the BfR can be divided into the following main cross-departmental areas:

Reference and consiliary laboratories

- Development of modern, sensitive detection methods that can supply fast and reliable data on the occurrence, spread and characterisation of pathogens, residues, contaminants and undesired ingredients

Risk assessment

- Collection of data on the occurrence, spread and intake of substances and microorganisms as the basis for exposure assessments
- Development of modern techniques for the detection of the toxic properties, active mechanisms and functionality of pathogens, substances and products as the basis for risk assessments
- Development of model parameters for prospective intake estimates of novel and functional foods as well as secondary plant ingredients
- Research in the field of exposure through chemicals in the household (e.g. in cosmetics, detergents etc.)
- Research in the field of exposure through textiles, toys and non-textile care articles
- Research into the carry-over of undesired substances from feed to food of animal origin as the basis for risk assessments
- Further development of probabilistic exposure assessment methods for the purpose of risk assessment
- Development of methods for the characterisation of uncertainties in exposure and risk assessments
- Development, validation and application of statistical and numerical methods at the interface of laboratory analysis and quantitative risk assessment
- Preparation of qualitative and quantitative risk assessments

Risk communication

- Elaboration of scientific principles for the adequate communication of risks while taking account of differences in perception, the communication of news via the media and risk-benefit considerations
- Research into mechanisms of risk perception of different stakeholders in the fields of science, industry, politics and the media as well as by associations, non-governmental organisations and consumers
- Development of methods for early risk detection incorporating social science models

- Research into the prediction of risk effects and risk assessments that might encourage higher-risk trade-offs
- Research into consumer behaviour in crisis situations and communication mechanisms in the event of crisis

Methods to replace and supplement animal experiments

- Documentation, assessment, development and validation of alternative methods to animal experiments with the aim of avoiding (replacement), reducing or improving (refinement) animal experiments ("3R principle")
- Development and validation of new, animal experiment-free safety toxicology testing methods in the fields of embryotoxicity / teratogenicity, phototoxicity and local toxicity to skin, eyes and lung
- Development of retrieval tools for methods to replace and supplement animal experiments
- Development of models, concepts and strategies to establish animal experiment-free methods

Risk identification, early risk detection and risk minimisation

- Research into food and product hygiene
- Development of modern methods for the detection and determination of the effects of potentially toxic substances that are formed in particular during the processing of food and feed
- Research into the recording and the effects of contaminants in food, feed and drinking water for animals including carry-over
- Biofunctionality of undesired substances in food and feed for the purpose of risk assessment
- (Further) development of molecular toxicology and computer-aided methods which permit reliable, rapid statements on toxic effects as the basis for risk assessments
- Research into the derivation of data-supported safety factors that can be used for the assessment of chemicals
- Investigations into the mechanisms of action of toxicologically relevant chemicals
- Research into potential applications of QSAR in the assessment of chemicals
- Research into the detection and mechanisms of action of toxic substances and their metabolites in chemical substances, consumer products, cosmetics, food and tobacco
- Research into the use and risks of nanotechnology in chemical substances, consumer items, cosmetic products and food as well as the toxicological testing of synthetically produced nanomaterials and exposure estimates for these materials
- Research into the allergenic effect of chemical substances in cosmetics and toys, in particular the migration of these substances to children, and research into the skin-sensitising effect of dyes and other chemicals in clothing and their migration to the skin or absorption via the skin
- Research into food safety in aquacultures
- Epidemiological and experimental risk assessment of aerosol sprays and investigation of testing methods

- Research into the influence of food technology methods on the behaviour of biological agents
- Improvements in the documentation and early detection of poisoning incidents in Germany
- Improvements in the use and operation of the BfR poison information database with particular emphasis on retrieval and data security aspects
- Mathematical models for the validation of diagnostic methods (e.g. validation without a gold standard)
- Epidemiological risk assessments for zoonotic diseases
- Research in the field of predictive microbiology
- Research into global product supply chains with regard to food safety
- Depiction and analysis of product supply chains with the help of specific software

III. Main areas of research of the departments and selected research projects

The core themes of the research projects of the various departments are listed below.

Risk Communication Department

- Measurement of risk perception of different stakeholders in the fields of science, industry, politics, the media, associations and NGOs as well as among consumers
- Survey to determine the information needs of the above stakeholders and development of communication tools for specific target groups
- Communication approach to scientific uncertainty
- Communication of risks in the media and the potential effects on behaviour
- Prevention of crises as well as coordination and communication in the event of crisis
- Evaluation of risk communication and the related participatory methods
- Risk communication on new technologies, especially nanotechnology
- Use of new media for risk communication

Selected research projects

- Development of a system to improve the exchange of information within the organisational infrastructure with the aim of faster detection, monitoring and management of EHEC and other human pathogenic bacteria in the value added chain for vegetables in the Euregio Rhine-Waal
- Antibiotics and antimicrobial resistance – analysis of media reporting as well as representative survey on knowledge, attitudes and practices among the population

Exposure Department

- Method development and first-time implementation of a Total Diet Study in Germany
- Germany-wide representative food consumption study for children (KiESEL) in order to generate data for exposure estimates
- Research into health risks of chemical substances occurring primarily in the transport of dangerous goods at sea or in marine applications (e.g. ballast water treatment)

- Improvements in the documentation and early detection of poisoning incidents in Germany
- Improvements in the use and operation of the BfR's poison information database with particular emphasis on retrieval and data security
- Development of space-time prediction models for aspects of food security in the context of global food chains
- Biometry, epidemiology and mathematical modelling and development of quantitative risk models
- Development of models to depict the statistical uncertainties in the estimation of frequency of illness or infection
- Validation of diagnostic tests without a gold standard
- Assessment of the statistical reliability of monitoring strategies
- Statistical methods for exploration and analysis of goods flows using graph theory/network analysis
- Development of models in the field of food and feed safety to describe the accumulation of contaminants in laboratory animals (e.g. dioxins)
- Development and application of computer-based evaluation programs for high-throughput data (e.g. in the field of proteomics)
- Development of predictive models for the spread of MRSA in livestock herds
- Exposure of the German population to environmental contaminants (heavy metals, dioxins and PCBs) through the consumption of food and consumer products
- Development of a database to record additives in food
- Further development of exposure scenarios under REACH
- Food exposure, improvement of the database and methodology for scientific assessments, inclusion of risk minimisation measures in exposure scenarios, taking account of consumer behaviour

Selected research projects

- Implementation of a nutritional study of children to document their food consumption (KiESEL)
- Development of strategies for the performance of a Europe-wide consumption study (under the lead management of EFSA) and a Europe-wide Total Diet Study

Biological Safety Department

- Research into the epidemiology of food-associated zoonoses, including antimicrobial resistance
- Development of monitoring programmes and modelling methods
- Research into the development of improved methods of exposure estimation and risk assessment
- Research into properties and virulence factors of food-associated pathogens and their tenacity and inactivation in food
- Research into the development and evaluation of new methods in the field of food hygiene and the development and validation of security concepts in food technology
- Research into horizontal gene transfer in food-related microorganisms
- Development of molecular biological detection methods, including microarrays and genome analysis (next generation sequencing)

- Research into food safety along global supply chains
- Research into bioterrorism with regard to questions of food safety and the development of suitable diagnostic and prevention methods
- Development of IT tools for the analysis of flows of goods
- Food safety and climate change
- Research into product hygiene and disinfection strategies
- Research into the detection and survival of human pathogens on plants

Selected research projects

- Securing the spices and herbs commodity chains in Europe against deliberate, accidental or natural biological and chemical contamination (SPICED)
- Zoonoses and food safety along global product supply chains (ZooGlow)

Food Safety Department

- Development of methods for the assessment of potential risks of functional and novel foods
- Identification of new biomarkers (exposure markers and effect markers; *in vitro* and *in vivo*) for risk estimation of food ingredients
- Research into the risks of especially vulnerable sections of the population
- Use and specification of proteomics and transcriptomics methods (toxicogenomics) and other modern molecular techniques for the toxicological assessment of food ingredients
- Molecular traceability and product identity
- Development and application of screening methods based on known or observed biological effects of substance classes that are of relevance in terms of food toxicology (effect-based analytics)
- Human studies to determine oral bioavailability and to identify and quantify biomarkers for exposure, effect and individual sensitivity
- Application of modern *in silico* techniques (e.g. (Q)SAR models) to predict the toxicity of food ingredients and implement these methods in the field of risk assessment

Selected research projects

- Modelling of the toxome of cultivated human hepatocytes (LivSys)
- Determining factors of the toxicity in intestine and liver for two similar sized nanoparticles used in food and packaging: In vitro and in vivo investigation on uptake and mechanisms involved (SolNanoTox)

Safety of Pesticides Department

- Endocrine disruptors: development of strategies and concepts for assessing plant protection products and biocides with regard to endocrine-damaging properties
- Risk assessment of multiple residues: research project on combination effects based on the example of a commonly used group of fungicides (triazoles)
- Improvement of knowledge on exposure to residues of plant protection products: analysis of consumption data and ongoing development of consumption models
- Improvement of toxicological bases for assessment: analysis of dermal absorption of the active substances of plant protection products
- Development of basic principles and strategies for risk assessment of nanomaterials in plant protection products and biocides

Selected research projects

- Investigation of mixture effects of pesticides in vitro (combiomics)
- Toxicity mechanisms of triazole fungicides

Chemicals and Product Safety Department

- Development of basic principles and strategies for the risk assessment of chemicals
- Migration, penetration/absorption, metabolism and toxicology of substances in commodities (e.g. food-contact materials, toys, clothes) in skin and lung with special regard to plasticisers (e.g. phthalates), perfluorinated compounds, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PACs), azo dyes (or their metabolites), metals and other compounds as well as nanomaterials
- Method development and validation for the highly sensitive analytical detection of these compounds and their metabolites in migrants, cell cultures and tissue cultures or as a basis for biomonitoring studies in serum or urine
- Detection and toxicological assessment of nanomaterials
- Safety of tattooing inks
- Development and validation of screening methods for sensitising, endocrine and genotoxic properties of chemical substances in consumer products (end points: sensitisation, endocrine disruption, epigenetics and genotoxicity)
- Analysis of consumer products (including tobacco) and their ingredients to determine tissue-specific toxicological characteristics while taking into account their metabolism

Selected research projects

- A common European approach to the regulatory testing of nanomaterials (NANoREG)
- Extent of metal release from food contact materials

Safety in the Food Chain Department

- Development of methods to detect potentially toxic substances like process-related contaminants, marine biotoxins and plant ingredients including their metabolites in food and feed
- Investigation of the occurrence of these substances in food and feed
- Validation and standardisation of analytical methods; e.g. within the framework of activities as a National Reference Laboratory (marine biotoxins, mycotoxins, PCBs and dioxins, additives in animal nutrition) to support risk assessment of the substances in question
- Further development of analytical methods and data interpretation techniques for the assessment of wine as senior expert office
- Research into the recording and effects of contaminants and undesired substances in food and feed as well as in drinking water for animals including carry-over
- Analysis of pesticides
- Research into the authenticity testing of wine and other food products
- Research into the traceability and safety of supply chains

Selected research projects

- Development and validation of an innovative analytical method for the selective determination of zearalenone in vegetable oils (ZENOL)
- Ensuring the Integrity of the European Food Chain (Food Integrity)

Experimental Toxicology and ZEBET Department

- Development and validation of alternative methods to replace animal tests entirely, reduce the number of animals in experiments and/or reduce the suffering of animals used in experiments
- Use of modern cell and molecular biology methods to promote the development of toxicological test methods
- Method development and mechanistic studies on toxicokinetic and mechanistic toxicological aspects as a basis for the risk assessment of chemicals
- Research into the production and standardisation of animal reference materials for the NRLs
- Food safety of aquatic organisms

Selected research projects

- Berlin-Brandenburg "B²3R" research platform with integrated Research Training Group on "Innovation in 3R Research – Genetic Engineering, Tissue Engineering and Bioinformatics"
- Development and validation of embryonic stem cell test systems